

Lepton flavour theories in the era of neutrino precision measurements

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Fundamental questions raised by neutrinos

● Smallness of neutrino masses

Talk by A. Vicente

Origin of neutrino mass

Seesaw mechanism,
nu mass models & B-L symmetry

Naturally embedded in

Grand Unified Theories (GUT)

● Largeness of lepton flavour mixing

Potential mixing patterns

Flavour symmetries
and flavour models

Era of neutrino precision measurements has come !

JUNO data first release

$$\sin^2 \theta_{12} = 0.3092 \pm 0.0087$$

$$\Delta m_{21}^2 = (7.50 \pm 0.12) \times 10^{-5} \text{ eV}^2$$

2511.14593

In coming years, **sub-percent level** of oscillation parameters will be measured

Mass ordering, CP violation, and θ_{23} octant will be solved.

Talks' by M. Sanchez & P. Denton

This talk will discuss

- How precision measurement of neutrino oscillation effects GUTs?

[1] Z. Q. Chen, G. X. Fang and Y. L. Zhou,
``Probing quark-lepton correlation in GUTs with high-precision neutrino measurements,``
[arXiv:2511.16196 [hep-ph]].

- How the precise data will tell us flavour mixing and flavour symmetries behind?

[2] W. H. Jiang, R. Ouyang, and Y. L. Zhou,
``Modular TM1 mixing in light of precision measurement in JUNO,``
[arXiv:2511.16348 [hep-ph]].

GUTs unify forces, also matters, and lead to rich phenomenology

- Unification of gauge symmetries

$$G_{\text{GUT}} \supset G_{\text{SM}} = SU(3)_C \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$$

- Unification of gauge couplings

Three gauge couplings, are running to be unified at the GUT scale

- Unification of matters

In SO(10), all matter fields are arranged in **16** representations

$$\nu_{L,R}, e_{L,R}, u_{L,R}^{1,2,3}, d_{L,R}^{1,2,3}$$

$$2 + 2 + 2 \times 3 + 2 \times 3 = 16$$

Quark-lepton correlation

King, Pascoli, Turner, **YLZ**, 2005.13549

Quark-lepton correlation in SO(10) GUTs

- Field arrangements: fermions $\sim \mathbf{16}$, $\mathbf{16} \times \mathbf{16} = \mathbf{10}_S + \mathbf{120}_A + \mathbf{126}_S$
 \Rightarrow Higgses $\sim \mathbf{10}, \overline{\mathbf{126}}, \mathbf{120}$ Dutta, Mimura, Mohapatra, hep-ph/0406262

- Quark-lepton correlation $\mathcal{L}_Y = \Psi_{16} \left[Y_{10} H_{10} + Y_{120} H_{120} + Y_{\overline{126}} H_{\overline{126}} \right] \Psi_{16}$

$$Y_u = c_{10}^u Y_{10} + c_{126}^u Y_{126} + (c_{120_1}^u + c_{120_{15}}^u) Y_{120} \quad Y_\nu = c_{10}^u Y_{10} - 3c_{126}^u Y_{126} + (c_{120_1}^u - 3c_{120_{15}}^u) Y_{120}$$

$$Y_u = c_{10}^d Y_{10} + c_{126}^d Y_{126} + (c_{120_1}^d + c_{120_{15}}^d) Y_{120} \quad M_R = v_S Y_{126}$$

$$Y_e = c_{10}^d Y_{10} - 3c_{126}^d Y_{126} + (c_{120_1}^d - 3c_{120_{15}}^d) Y_{120} \quad M_\nu = Y_{126} v_\Delta - Y_\nu M_R^{-1} Y_\nu^T v^2$$

General formula with
Peccei-Quinn symm

- A complete list of possible combinations of Higgs content in renormalisable SO(10) GUTs

Higgs content	Whether realistic in fitting fermion data
Only one Higgs	No, no flavor mixing
$10_H^{\mathbb{R},\mathbb{C}}, 120_H^{\mathbb{R},\mathbb{C}}$	No, massless light neutrinos
$10_H^{\mathbb{R}}, \overline{126}_H^{\mathbb{C}}$	No, small hierarchy between m_b and m_t
$120_H^{\mathbb{R},\mathbb{C}}, \overline{126}_H^{\mathbb{C}}$	No, inconsistent with mixing data
$10_H^{\mathbb{C}}, \overline{126}_H^{\mathbb{C}}$	Yes, imposing $U(1)_{\text{PQ}}$ leads to Model 1
$10_H^{\mathbb{R}}, \overline{126}_H^{\mathbb{C}}, 120_H^{\mathbb{R}}$	Yes, assuming SCPV leads to Model 2
$10_H^{\mathbb{C}}, \overline{126}_H^{\mathbb{C}}, 120_H^{\mathbb{C}}$	Yes, imposing $U(1)_{\text{PQ}} \times Z_2^P$ leads to Model 3

We perform scan of these models
Chen, Fang, **YLZ**, 2511.16196

Predictions via quark-lepton correlation

- Model 1, $(\mathbf{10}_C, \overline{\mathbf{126}}_C)$ with $U(1)_{PQ}$
the minimal Higgs content

of free parameters: $n_{\text{para}} = 19$

$$Y_u = S + D$$

$$Y_d = r_2 S + e^{i\omega} r_1 D$$

$$Y_e = r_2 S - 3e^{i\omega} r_1 D$$

$$Y_\nu = S - 3D$$

$$M_R = v_R D,$$

$$M_\nu = -Y_\nu M_R^{-1} Y_\nu^T v^2$$

Altarelli, Meloni, 1305.1001;
Babu, Khan, 1507.06717;
Ohlsson, Pernow, 1903.08241;
Mummidi, Patel, 2109.04050

- Normal ordering
- No strong prediction on CPV
- $0\nu\beta\beta$ testable
- Prediction on RHN masses
large hierarchy

- B-L breaking scale $> 10^{12-13}$ GeV
- Thermal leptogenesis favoured

$n_{\text{obs}} = 18$

Predictions via quark-lepton correlation

- Model 2, $(\mathbf{10}_R, \overline{\mathbf{126}}_C, \mathbf{120}_R)$ with SCPV

All Yukawa at GUT scales are real

of free parameters: $n_{\text{para}} = 19$

$$Y_u = e^{i\alpha}S + D + e^{i\lambda}A$$

$$Y_d = e^{-i\alpha}S + e^{i\omega}r_1D + e^{-i\lambda}A$$

$$Y_e = e^{-i\alpha}S - 3e^{i\omega}r_1D + e^{-i\gamma}r_4A \quad M_R = v_R D,$$

$$Y_\nu = e^{i\alpha}S - 3D + e^{i\gamma}r_4A$$

$$M_\nu = -Y_\nu M_R^{-1} Y_\nu^T v^2$$

Babu, Bajc, Saad, 1612.04329;

Saad, 2212.05291;

Babu, Di Bari, Fong, Saad, 2409.03840

Babu, Fong, Saad, 2508.14969

- Normal ordering
- CPV not maximal
- $0\nu\beta\beta$ not testable
- Prediction on RHN masses super-large hierarchy,
- $M_1 \sim (10^5, 10^8)$ GeV, regime not found before

- B-L breaking scale close to GUT scale
- Leptogenesis: Davidson-Ibarra bound not satisfied
- ⇒ N_2 leptogenesis?

$n_{\text{obs}} = 18$

Predictions via quark-lepton correlation

- Model 3, $(\mathbf{10}_C, \overline{\mathbf{126}}_C, \mathbf{120}_C)$ with $U(1)_{PQ} \times Z_2^P$

All Yukawa's at EW scale are Hermitian

Minimal free parameters: $n_{\text{para}} = 18$

$$Y_u = S + D + iA$$

$$Y_d = r_2 S + r_1 D + ir_3 A$$

$$Y_e = r_2 S - 3r_1 D + ir_4 A \quad M_R = v_R D,$$

$$Y_\nu = S - 3D + ir_5 A \quad M_\nu = -Y_\nu M_R^{-1} Y_\nu^T v^2$$

Joshipura, Patel, 1102.5148

Dueck, Rodejohann, 1306.4468

Fu, King, Marsili, Pascoli,

Turner, YLZ, 2209.00021

- Normal ordering
- CP violation not maximal
- $0\nu\beta\beta$ partially testable
- Prediction on RHN masses smaller hierarchy

- B-L breaking scale less restricted
- Thermal leptogenesis works

$n_{\text{obs}} = 18$

Discrete symmetries as origin of flavour mixing

We assume the flavour symmetry to be S_4

$$T^3 = S^2 = (ST)^3 = 1$$

$$U^2 = (SU)^2 = (TU)^2 = (STU)^4 = 1$$

Two 3-dim faithful representations $\mathbf{3}$ and $\mathbf{3}'$

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \omega^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \omega \end{pmatrix} \quad S = \frac{1}{3} \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 2 & 2 \\ 2 & -1 & 2 \\ 2 & 2 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$U = \pm \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$SU = \pm \frac{1}{3} \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 2 & 2 \\ 2 & 2 & -1 \\ 2 & -1 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$$

presented in the Altarelli-Feruglio basis

From TBM to TM mixing

- Tri-bimaximal (TBM)

$$U_{\text{TBM}} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{2}{\sqrt{6}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ -\frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{array}{l} \text{Harrison,} \\ \text{Perkins,} \\ \text{Scott, 02;} \\ \text{Xing, 02} \end{array}$$

$$\sin^2 \theta_{12} = \frac{1}{3} \quad \theta_{23} = 45^\circ \quad \theta_{13} = 0$$

- Trimaximal TM_1 vs TM_2

$$U_{\text{TM}_1} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{2}{\sqrt{6}} & \times & \times \\ -\frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & \times & \times \\ -\frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & \times & \times \end{pmatrix} \begin{array}{l} \text{Xing, S.Zhou,} \\ \text{0607302; Lam,} \\ \text{0611017;} \\ \text{Albright,} \\ \text{Rodejohann,} \\ \text{0812.0436} \end{array}$$

$$\sin^2 \theta_{12} = 1 - \frac{2}{3(1 - \sin^2 \theta_{13})}$$

$$\theta_{23} \approx 45^\circ + \sqrt{2}\theta_{13} \cos \delta,$$

$$U_{\text{TM}_2} = \begin{pmatrix} \times & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & \times \\ \times & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & \times \\ \times & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & \times \end{pmatrix} \begin{array}{l} \text{Bjorken, Harrison,} \\ \text{Scott, 0511201;} \\ \text{He, Zee, 0607163;} \\ \text{Grimus, Lavoura,} \\ \text{0809.0226;} \\ \text{0810.4516} \end{array}$$

$$\sin^2 \theta_{12} = \frac{1}{3(1 - \sin^2 \theta_{13})}$$

$$\theta_{23} \approx 45^\circ + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\theta_{13} \cos \delta.$$

TM2 is not consistent with new data, if special RG effects not included

For more discussions on RG effect, see D. Zhang, 2511.15654

TM1 is consistent with new data in 1σ range

We review on data-driven flavour model building in modular symmetry

Jiang, Ouyang, YLZ, 2511.16348

TM₁ in traditional flavour symmetry approach

- “classical” flavour model

Traditional approach vs modular-invariant approach

- “classical” flavour model

$$\gamma \in G_f = S_4$$

$$\psi \rightarrow \rho_I(\gamma)\psi$$

$$Y(\{\phi_i\}) \rightarrow \rho_{I_Y}(\gamma)Y(\{\phi_i\})$$

- Flavour model with modular symmetry

$$\gamma \in \Gamma_4 \simeq S_4$$

$$\tau \rightarrow \gamma\tau = \frac{a\tau + b}{c\tau + d}$$

$$\psi \rightarrow (c\tau + d)^{2k} \rho_I(\gamma)\psi$$

$$Y(\tau) \rightarrow (c\tau + d)^{2k_Y} \rho_{I_Y}(\gamma)Y(\tau)$$

Symmetry

Matter field

Yukawa couplings

- If the lepton has non-vanishing modular weight, the modular symmetry can be directly used to explain flavour mixing

Feruglio, 1706.08749

TM1 in modular-invariant approaches

Including both flavons and one modular field

Kobayashi, Tanaka, Tatsuishi, 1803.10391

Multiple moduli field approach

de Medeiros Varzielas,
King, **YLZ**, 1906.02208;
King, **YLZ**, 1908.02770

$$\tau_T = \omega = -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

$$\tau_{SU} = -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}$$

Model details

Fermions	S_4	$2k$	Scalars	S_4	$2k$	Modular forms	S_4	$2k$
e^c	1	-5	φ_ℓ	3	+2	$Y_2(\tau_\nu)$	2	+2
μ^c	1'	-2	η	2	-1	$Y_{3'}(\tau_\nu)$	3'	+2
τ^c	1	-2	ξ	1'	0			
L	3	+1	$H_{u,d}$	1	0			
ν^c	3	-1						

Each model has only **five** real parameters

to predict **all** observables in the neutrino sector

$$W = \frac{y_e}{\Lambda^2} (L\varphi_\ell^2)_1 e^c H_d + \frac{y_\mu}{\Lambda^2} (L(\varphi_\ell\eta)_{3'})_{1'} \mu^c H_d + \frac{y_\tau}{\Lambda^2} (L(\varphi_\ell\eta)_3)_1 \tau^c H_d \\ + y_D L\nu^c H_u + \frac{1}{2} Y_2(\tau_\nu) (\nu^c\nu^c)_2 \xi + \frac{1}{2} Y_{3'}(\tau_\nu) (\nu^c\nu^c)_3 \xi.$$

Fermions	S_4	$2k$	Scalars	S_4	$2k$	Modular forms	S_4	$2k$
e^c	1'	-6	φ_ν	3	0	$Y_e(\tau_l)$	3'	+6
μ^c	1'	-4	φ'_ν	3'	0	$Y_\mu(\tau_l)$	3'	+4
τ^c	1'	-2	η	1'	0	$Y_\tau(\tau_l)$	3'	+2
L	3	0	$H_{u,d}$	1	0			
ν^c	3	0						

$$W = Y_e(\tau_l) L e^c H_d + Y_\mu(\tau_l) L \mu^c H_d + Y_\tau(\tau_l) L \tau^c H_d \\ + y_D (L\nu^c)_1 H_u + \frac{1}{2} M_1(\nu^c\nu^c)_1 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \varphi_\nu (\nu^c\nu^c)_3 + \frac{\lambda'}{2\Lambda} \varphi'_\nu (\nu^c\nu^c\eta)_{3'}$$

Fields	S_4^l	S_4^ν	$2k_l$	$2k_\nu$
e^c	1'	1	-6	-2
μ^c	1'	1	-4	-2
τ^c	1'	1	-2	-2
L	3	1	0	+2
ν^c	1	3	0	-2
Φ	3	3	0	0
$H_{u,d}$	1	1	0	0

$$W = Y_e(\tau_l) L e^c H_d + Y_\mu(\tau_l) L \mu^c H_d + Y_\tau(\tau_l) L \tau^c H_d \\ + \frac{y_\nu}{\Lambda} L \Phi H_u \nu^c + \frac{1}{2} M_1(\tau_\nu) (\nu^c\nu^c)_1 + \frac{1}{2} M_2(\tau_\nu) (\nu^c\nu^c)_2 + \frac{1}{2} M_3(\tau_\nu) (\nu^c\nu^c)_3.$$

Model A

Model B

Model C

Predictions

- Main feature of flavour models in modular invariant approach

$$M_R = c_1 \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + c_2 \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} + c_3 \sqrt{2} \begin{pmatrix} 2 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & 2 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & 2 \end{pmatrix} - c_3 \sqrt{3} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 2 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & -2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Impossible to achieved in traditional flavour symmetry approach

- Predictions on mass observables in each models

第五届JUNO相关的理论和唯象研讨会 首个物理成果专题研讨会

Specified Workshop on First Physical Achievement in JUNO

2026年1月27-30日 杭州 · HANGZHOU

<https://indico.ihep.ac.cn/event/27960/>

Conclusion

- We are in the precision era of neutrino measurement now.
- Quark-lepton correlation will play important role in the testability of GUTs.
- We take former global-fit data and new JUNO data to scan flavour space of SO(10) GUTs.
 - Normal ordering favoured, predicted regimes of CPV, $0\nu\beta\beta$ mass, prediction on RHN masses ...
 - Restriction on B-L breaking scale, bridge to leptogenesis
- New data point to Trimaximal TM1 mixing. It supports S4 symmetry, and Z3 and Z2 as residual symmetry in charged lepton and neutrino sector after the spontaneous breaking of S4
- TM1 can be achieved both in traditional flavour symmetry approach and modular-invariant approach. We show different prediction on observables of effective masses in different models

Thanks and questions ...

Backup: benchmarks in SO(10) GUTs

Physical Quantity	M1		M2		M3 with NO		M3 with IO	
	BM1N1	BM1N2	BM2N1	BM2N2	BM3N1	BM3N2	BM3I2 [SK]	BM3I2
$y_u/10^{-6}$	4.1841	4.08227	2.81639	7.43413	2.57195	2.51847	2.43426	2.65498
$y_c/10^{-3}$	1.40605	1.37123	1.36956	1.38067	1.35808	1.36456	1.17039	1.22564
y_t	0.428387	0.42744	0.428109	0.427893	0.428165	0.427999	0.430395	0.430358
$y_d/10^{-6}$	1.90741	2.33024	3.81711	6.40586	7.63478	6.50436	9.56856	9.50973
$y_s/10^{-4}$	1.20008	1.35263	1.17849	1.35147	1.22573	1.22668	1.54642	1.54173
$y_b/10^{-2}$	0.56536	0.572574	0.569053	0.569561	0.569812	0.571195	0.565933	0.565299
$y_e/10^{-6}$	2.70615	2.70217	2.70694	2.70512	2.7012	2.70299	2.70194	2.70201
$y_\mu/10^{-4}$	5.67557	5.64767	5.72306	5.68859	5.70761	5.70903	5.70879	5.70885
$y_\tau/10^{-2}$	0.979853	0.971086	0.968229	0.969382	0.968972	0.968018	0.96074	0.961776
θ_{12}^q	0.227388	0.227475	0.226987	0.227082	0.22744	0.227423	0.22722	0.227252
$\theta_{23}^q/10^{-2}$	4.78722	4.86052	4.8502	4.85534	4.86112	4.86603	4.80717	4.7965
$\theta_{13}^q/10^{-3}$	4.44527	4.36218	4.15777	4.03305	4.19948	4.19105	4.05637	4.09738
δ^q	1.10098	1.20818	1.17491	1.15692	1.25108	1.23699	1.16523	1.17458
$\Delta m_{21}^2/10^{-5}$ eV	7.49642	7.51729	7.48813	7.3983	7.4778	7.49186	7.49294	7.49265
$\Delta m_{3\ell}^2/10^{-3}$ eV	2.51096	2.53253	2.51289	2.53819	2.51446	2.53476	-2.48323	-2.50876
$\sin^2\theta_{12}^l$	0.306389	0.315291	0.299572	0.28436	0.306322	0.307802	0.308057	0.308222
$\sin^2\theta_{23}^l$	0.469948	0.551379	0.444945	0.561499	0.484914	0.566208	0.56614	0.581098
$\sin^2\theta_{13}^l$	0.021243	0.0210321	0.0223411	0.0223394	0.0219516	0.0218592	0.0222424	0.0221835
$\chi^2/(n_{\text{obs}} = 18)$	3.87235	3.09649	1.33774	2.64746	0.267685	0.0398901	4.37628	3.6284
$m_{\text{lightest}}/\text{eV}$	0.0042892	0.0058079	0.00004451	0.00027735	0.00078667	0.00034488	0.0209164	0.0211369
m_β/eV	0.0097066	0.0104976	0.0088360	0.0087947	0.00884413	0.00883645	0.0530547	0.0533778
$m_{\beta\beta}/\text{eV}$	0.0045207	0.0076123	0.0036564	0.0036244	0.00414862	0.00390756	0.0499542	0.0504771
$\delta/^\circ$	285.682	208.427	350.862	310.236	346.342	339.851	79.9639	84.8719
M_1/GeV	1.15×10^9	1.43×10^9	6.06×10^4	2.56×10^6	6.56×10^9	1.26×10^{10}	3.26×10^9	3.12×10^9
M_2/GeV	1.74×10^{11}	1.72×10^{11}	4.28×10^{12}	7.44×10^{11}	1.37×10^{11}	2.28×10^{11}	6.68×10^{10}	6.48×10^{10}
M_3/GeV	3.11×10^{12}	3.05×10^{12}	1.29×10^{15}	2.15×10^{14}	6.26×10^{12}	5.52×10^{12}	6.09×10^{12}	6.02×10^{12}